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Not Disabled , Just Differently Abled

Shabib Md. Shadakatul Baree

Several years ago I saw a movie called 'Rain Man', which made me think a new about differently-abled people. After that I saw the movie 'A Beautiful Mind' and 'My Left Foot'. The three movies were wonderful, close to life, rich in information and heart touching. I watched, and wept bitterly. After watching it, I was so depressed that I decided never to watch such a movie again. But what I got about schizophrenia, cerebral palsy, savant syndrome, etc. made me a different person, opened my eyes, broke many of my misconceptions. I realized that a person with savant syndrome, which we consider a bit unusual, but I was surprised to know how much knowledge that person can hold in their head and recall that information quickly. I saw that the man could only control his left leg from childhood, but once he became one of the world's best writers and painters. How a man with schizophrenia can also be a great mathematician, with hand-made mathematical theories.

When we were kids, we only knew about physically challenged people. They were taught at home and in the municipal policy books, 'Don't call the lame lame', 'Don't call the deaf,' 'Don't call the dumb dumb', they get hurt - that's it. I didn't even know there was such a thing as mental retardation. Not much was told or taught about it. We knew that someone with mental imbalance was called crazy. We used to say the same. For example, my father's friend's son was my age. He didn't talk much, he didn't mix with people that much, he didn't play when we went for a walk. But surprisingly, he could draw incredibly well. He could draw exactly whomever he saw. We were surprised but never understood this quality of his, no one appreciated, not even his parents. Rather, they also avoided people, neighbors.

Similarly we are never taught that these differently abled people are not from another world, not alien beings. These are the people next to us, who have immense power. Those who are a little or a lot different in behavior, but there is hidden talent in them. They have to be loved, taken, encouraged. The most important thing is to think of the child and pull him to the chest. We all

always avoid them, avoid them. They are not mentally ill or perversely called 'crazy'. We cannot think of any disabled or differently abled person as us. I don't give importance to their suffering, wants and needs. Marginalize them, hide them, deprive them of all rights. Those of us who think we are 'Able' are actually the most 'Disable' and it is proven.

In this connection, I remembered an older child who lived on the sixth floor of my aunt's building with his mother. While coming and going, they would suddenly meet on the way. When his mother used to walk with the child, it could be understood that she was holding a great pain in her chest. He used to enter the house with the child very surrenderingly, hiding his face and eyes. Even sometimes they were not saved. The child used to defecate and urinate inside the elevator. We used to get upset about it and express regret. So maybe the 17-year-old boy's mother used to hide her face out of shame. The mother of the disabled child was helpless, as the doctor told her to take the child outside for a walk every day, or she would get sicker. So in this big family, the child's mother was forced to do this unpleasant task. That stupid child in my aunt's building passed away years ago after ending all his mother's suffering. His mother kept crying like a mad man saying, "I couldn't sleep because of him. I just thought that if I die leaving him, who will see him? Today he left with his head in my hand, will I sleep tonight?" There is no answer to this question.

I knew another mother who, unable to bear the pain, said, "I would strangle my child if I could. But I couldn't, I can't. I'm just afraid that if I don't have her father, where will she go in this world? He will die and suffer." He said this and wept bitterly. "But you know, he is the one I love the most out of my three children. I think about him all the time." This cousin of mine was also physically challenged. Just one year after the boy died, his mother, my aunt also died. He died without thought.

I came to know, understand and feel with my heart about this 'autism' and 'autistic' issue much later. It is a neurodevelopmental disorder that lasts a lifetime. Earlier people did not understand this matter. Not that he understands much yet. While the educated people of the city know something of necessity, countless people in the villages know nothing. To them they are known as 'crazy'.

We have to campaign a lot about disability and autism, make people aware. Parents need to be made aware that they observe their child's behavior from an early age. For example, is the child not speaking on time, not making eye contact, acting on his own, not wanting to do anything out of routine, not accepting any change, repeating the same behavior over and over again, etc. Parents who have a child with a physical or mental disability know the hardships they go through. In this country, in this society, they accept the terrible odds and bring up a disabled child. While raising a healthy child properly is the most difficult task for a parent, it is easy to imagine what a physically or mentally challenged child might be like.

Government orphanages are home to children, often they pick up disabled children from different places or the police come and pass them here. These children are not only unwanted, but seriously unwanted. Their mothers or fathers refuse guardianship of disabled children and leave them in the water, in the forest or on the roadside. These children are deprived of almost all basic rights. No one looks after them, cares, loves them except father, mother especially mother. Everyone thinks of them as a burden to the family or society. Society shuns them more than they shun a dishonest, scoundrel, lustful, murderer. Children with disabilities are neglected, unloved. Although these people have some value in urban, middle-class or rich families, they are thought of by the family to some extent, but in poor families they are just a burden. Many are used for begging. But as long as these helpless people live in any family, they remain as a burden to the family. Only their mother or father thinks about them, loves them. But if the state really stands by them, then the suffering of the family can be reduced a lot. As has happened in the developed world.

A little love, a little support, a little change of perspective, a little kindness, a little helping hand can give these differently abled people the strength to survive. They are our children, not aliens. We should all think that at some point in time, a child may be born into one's family, who is disabled with white eyes but who may be differently abled. There are different types of energy hidden in each of them, which it is our responsibility to awaken. The family, the society, the state should not hide the autistic child and give him the opportunity to mix with everyone. What an

autistic child needs most is understanding. What are the qualities hidden inside the child? He should always be encouraged. A special treatment system has been introduced for them in the country. Although not all hospitals, not even all doctors know how to deal with this patient, not all schools teach these children. But still we hope - one day we will understand them, embrace them, learn to respect them.